

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Agronomic evaluation of some leading cultivars for the Turkish rice breeding program

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The evaluation of the world's leading rice material — the first and most important step in rice improvement — not only facilitates selection of the most suitable parents, but also enhances their cultivation.

Agronomic characters of the material listed in the table, evaluated for 3 years, indicate that:

- Cultivars of Italian origin (grown widely in Turkey) did not perform as well as U.S. and Russian cultivars. But U.S. varieties needed a longer vegetative period and Russian varieties had smaller kernels.
- Despite its shorter culms and higher tiller number, the indica group was unsuitable because of other problems. The same was true for indica-japonica hybrids.
- No superior agronomic characteristics

Performance (3-yr av) at Izmir, Turkey, of 18 rice varieties and lines of different origins.

Variety	Grain yield (g/plant)	Panicles (no./plant)	Grains (no./plant)	T.K.W. ^a (g)	Maturity ^b (days)	Plant ht (cm)
<i>IRRI</i>						
IR747B2	12.6	16.2	53.1	18.54	110	62
IR1561-228-3	11.2	13.8	59.1	17.96	133	64
IR2037-625	14.0	12.6	83.1	16.86	123	59
IR2307-64	23.1	14.5	94.3	20.81	119	65
IR2307-117	12.7	14.4	71.5	15.27	128	62
<i>TURKEY</i>						
Dawn (USA)	13.8	5.7	124.4	21.81	120	100
Tongil (Korean)	12.0	8.2	78.2	26.12	116	56
Sarikilçik	11.1	12.0	34.8	32.62	77	81
Akçeltik	10.9	10.5	41.1	27.96	83	96
Sariçeltik	14.4	10.1	56.2	27.01	97	109
<i>USSR</i>						
Kuban	16.1	9.6	87.5	26.31	82	91
Krasnodorky 424	14.4	7.6	114.3	27.32	83	100
<i>ITALY</i>						
Ribe	13.1	6.2	71.4	29.62	88	85
Baldo	14.0	7.0	71.3	34.71	84	82
Rocca	12.5	7.9	64.8	30.95	88	83
<i>USA</i>						
Caloro	13.5	6.3	112.6	24.58	122	104
CS-S4	15.8	7.5	108.7	23.76	122	103
Calrose	27.2	11.1	129.5	24.02	122	104
LSD 5%	3.00	2.29	10.95	0.90	—	3.28

^aThousand kernel wt. ^bDays from seeding to harvest.

were observed among the local varieties, except for the shorter

vegetative period in the cultivar Sarikilçik. ■

Breeding behavior of a cross between two lowland varieties

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Pankaj (P₁) and O.C. 1393 (P₂) were crossed at Chinsurah in 1976 kharif in a program to develop intermediate height, high yielding genotypes suitable for the lowlands where water level fluctuates (10–15 cm) depending on rainfall.

O.C. 1393 is a strongly photoperiod-sensitive local variety adapted to the lowlands, and Pankaj (a selection of IR5), is the only high yielding variety widely cultivated in the lowlands during kharif in West Bengal.

F₁ seeds from the cross were grown in the field in 1977 kharif. Photoperiod

sensitivity is considered an essential trait for varieties grown during this season. Therefore, F₂ populations were sown in January and grown during 1978 boro to separate early, long-duration, and photoperiod sensitive segregates. More than 60% of the plants flowered by May; the remaining plants flowered at the end of October or in November and, at 22°52'N latitude, were assumed to be photoperiod responsive. O.C. 1393 flowered only in November 1978 whereas Pankaj flowered irregularly.

Seeds from the individual photoperiod sensitive plants (F₃) and the two parents were grown in lowland plots at IRRI during the 1979 dry season.

Seedling heights at 21 days after seeding (DS) averaged 41.7 cm for O.C. 1393, 30.9 cm for Pankaj, and

39.5 cm for the F₃ population with a range of 30–52 cm. The F₃ population consisted of intermediate or semitall types with an inclination toward O.C. 1393, the taller parent. A transgressive segregation toward the taller types, shown by the range, may be due to a gene for tallness in Pankaj, which is lacking in O.C. 1393. When the two varieties are crossed, the combination of genes produces plants taller than O.C. 1393.

The frequency distribution of F₃ seedling heights showed a normal curve (see figure). This character appears to be polygenic in nature and wide segregates in the F₃ population indicate a possibility of producing intermediate plants from the population.

At 31 DS the F₃ population and the